

THE EFFICIENCY OF USING A SMART PASTURE

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Abstract

Meat cattle breeding remains a weak link in Kazakhstan's animal husbandry. The main conditions for breeding specialized beef cattle are the availability of pastures for which there is a shortage of labour. Also, one of the problems is using fields in the old-fashioned way, which leads to severe degradation. Therefore, to develop recommendations for the development of new technologies in meat cattle breeding and solving the problems mentioned above, researchers of the S. Seifullin KATRU introduced a "Smart" pasture of their design in the North Kazakhstan Agricultural Experimental Station LLP of the Akkayyn district, North Kazakhstan region, which opens up opportunities for reducing labour-intensive work due to the shortage of agricultural equipment, workers (shepherds), reducing the degradation of pastures and increasing the weight gain of animals.

Keywords: pastures, economic efficiency, "Smart" pastures, pasture lands, farmers, beef cattle.

Relevance. There is a need for more pasture land in almost all regions of Kazakhstan. Based on the results of meetings of deputies with farmers, senators initiated and developed draft laws to resolve issues with pastures and more effective solutions to problems in this area. According to deputies, about 80% of the livestock is grazed on heavily degraded pastures within and around villages, which is about 21 million hectares. Today's estimated need for grazing livestock in a private farmstead is 50 million hectares, deficit-29 million hectares [1].

Where there are farm animals, pastures are used old-fashioned without applying scientific-based standards, rotation, coefficients of completeness of use, etc. The soil and vegetation cover is satisfactory, with no animals (non-watered pastures).

The question arises of how to change the situation in pasture areas, which are annually renewed with 23-25 million tons of feed unit feed resources. It is becoming clear that the farmers themselves, who use such land, should improve the condition of pastures along with administrative institutions of power. To do this, the land users must have the minimum knowledge that will allow them to maintain an ecological balance on the land plots used [2,3].

The way out of this situation is to improve the economic efficiency of fattening cattle by developing new production technologies, that is, using "Smart" pasture technologies, the effect of which is seen in the following scheme 1.

Research results and discussion. The study was conducted according to the data of "North Kazakhstan Agricultural Experimental Station" LLP in Akkayyn district, North Kazakhstan region.

From the total area of pastures of the farm, for organizing grazing by the corral (portion) method, the scientists of KATRU selected a separate section of the experimental "Smart" pasture with an area of 70 hectares, with seven corrals of an average of 10 hectares. The

pens were arranged in a petal shape with a separate single exit to the watering hole. The development was carried out according to the following concept:

1. Automatic livestock tracking;
2. Natural grazing of animals;
3. Control of drinking animals;
4. Remote control of live weight;
5. Automatic processing of animals;
6. Automatic accounting of forage capacity of pastures.

For the experiment, animals of 56 cows, three bulls and 44 calves were grazed alternately in paddocks. Sources of drinking water for livestock - a well

with a depth of 35 meters at a depth of 100 m. Here are the calculations for determining the cost, Figure 1.

Figure 1. "Smart" pastures

Hence, the approximate cost of a smart pasture is 11,092,467. 74 тенге = (the cost of components is 8,992,452 тенге + the cost of preparation is 2,100,015. 74 тенге. It should be borne in mind that the cost may vary depending on prices and components, and the cost

does not include the cost of services of research workers. Costs per 1 ha/тенге (including the total pasture area of 70 ha) amounted to 158,463.8.

The economic feasibility of a " smart " pasture on the farm is shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Economic efficiency of "Smart" pasture

Indicators	Technology		+ . -
	Traditional	Smart pasture	
Number of employees engaged in grazing, people	4	2	-2
Average working hours, people/hour per month	1 080	540	- 540
Average monthly salary costs with deduction, thousand tenge	944,6	472,3	-472,3
Average daily weight gain, grams	720	850	+130

As you can see from the table, work is reduced to a minimum (there is no need to work all day). A worker's labour can only be used when changing the path of pasture or moving to a new one. Animals need to be watered and water updated daily, so two workers are enough since the worker will take a little time – up to an hour or a little longer, but not the whole working day. "Smart" pasture also solves the problem of a shortage of shepherds since no one wants to graze cattle in the country.

By avoiding daily grazing under the supervision of a shepherd, it is possible to recoup the costs of acquiring "Smart" pastures in a short time (by saving the wage

fund almost twice): The payback period will be $PP=IC/CF= 2$ years.

Regardless of the area of pasture, the following advantages of "Smart" pastures can be distinguished:

The main advantage is associated with minimizing the cost of a human shepherd:

- If with traditional technology, ten or more employees were involved in sanitary work, and this whole procedure harmed the animal (the animal received stress, which led to weight loss), then with "Smart" pastures, these procedures are performed automatically and without stress for the animals. Therefore, it simplifies the implementation of preventive measures.

Conclusion. Low cost and fast payback. And even these costs can be reduced. A simple design of "Smart" pastures can be made independently – they make poles, buy metal mesh and wire, and use a solar station or a car battery as a power source from an economic point of view.

The easy-to-use kit is easy to reinstall when changing the boundaries of the pasture or switching to a new one from a technical point of view.

From an ecological point of view, efficiency is considered from the point of view that it becomes convenient for farmers to control the restoration of vegetation in the areas allocated for pasture. Livestock in the new place receives abundant food, and the correct distribution of fields solves the problem of measures for their degradation.

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